

MOBILE PHONE DEPENDENCE, ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE AND QUALITY OF LIFE OF TERTIARY LEVEL STUDENTS

Hannah Sophia H. Sanchez, Yra Ishi L. Suarez, Renz Paulo N. Bengco,
Apple L. Banag, Krizia C. Dela Cruz, Joseph Michael D. Manlutac

Nursing Department, University of the Assumption, Pampanga, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

In the digital age, mobile phones have become essential tools, yet their excessive use has raised concerns about dependence and its effects on life aspects. This study investigated the impact of mobile phone dependence on academic performance and quality of life among tertiary students. A quantitative approach with a descriptive, comparative, correlational, and predictive design was employed. The study surveyed 349 students selected through stratified proportionate random sampling from a Catholic university in San Fernando, Pampanga. Data were collected using a three-part survey covering demographics, the Smartphone Compulsion Test, and the WHOQOL-BREF. Results showed a high level of mobile dependence among respondents, with 85.10% scoring above the dependence threshold. Most respondents reported moderate satisfaction with their overall quality of life, yet many experienced negative psychological and physical health symptoms. Significant differences were found between academic performance and social relationships, suggesting that stronger social ties may positively impact academic outcomes. A significant difference was also observed in mobile dependence across different durations of mobile use, though not strictly proportional. Notably, mobile phone use for academic purposes was associated with lower general weighted averages. Correlational analysis revealed a significant negative relationship between mobile dependence and quality of life across all domains, while academic performance positively correlated with quality of life. Interestingly, mobile dependence demonstrated a positive relationship with academic performance, suggesting the evolving role of technology in education. The findings underscore the importance of promoting balanced mobile phone use to support students' academic success and well-being.

Keywords: *Mobile phone dependence, Academic performance, Quality of life, Smartphone, Tertiary-level students, Technology*

INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of digital use has transformed mobile phones into multifaceted devices that serve as an essential tool in daily lives. Individuals can access information, connect with others despite the distance and engage in dynamic updates of varied entertainments (Ratan et al., 2022). However, while the advancement of the mobile phones significantly enhanced connectivity and productivity, it also sparked growing concerns of potential harmful impacts for overuse (Harris et al., 2020). The pervasive mobile phone usage increasingly influences various dimensions of human well-being, including academic performance and overall quality of life (Mei et al., 2018).

Mobile phone dependence—often referred interchangeably with smartphone addiction and characterized by excessive, uncontrollable usage patterns that persist even with an occurrence of negative physical, psychological, social and academic domains, impairing an individual’s daily functioning (Moattari et al., 2017). Among students, in particular, such dependency has particularly detrimental implications for academic success. The inappropriate use of smartphones in academic settings often leads to distraction, hinders active participation, ultimately disrupting the learning process (Mahsud et al., 2020).

Beyond academic concerns, mobile phone dependence also poses risks to students' overall quality of life. Prolonged screen time is associated with sedentary behavior, weight gain, sleep disturbances, and other lifestyle-related health issues, all of which collectively diminish well-being and life satisfaction (Alotaibi et al., 2022). These factors underscore the urgent need to understand and address smartphone overuse among students.

Despite the increasing global discourse on mobile phone dependency, there remains a notable lack of localized research that explores the complex relationship between mobile phone dependence, academic outcomes, and well-being particularly among tertiary students. This study seeks to address that gap by exploring the extent to which mobile phone reliance affects the academic performance and quality of life of students. By doing so, the research aims to contribute to the development of informed strategies that promote healthier digital habits and support student success— thereby fostering improved academic outcomes and enhancing overall well-being.

Literature Review

According to Statista (as cited in Ratan et al., 2022), 83.72% of the global population—over 6 billion people—were reported to be using mobile phones. With the convenience these devices bring, many individuals use them constantly, leading to the emergence of “nomophobia” (no mobile phone phobia). This term refers to the fear or anxiety individuals feel when they are without their mobile phone or unable to use it (Notara et al., 2021).

Research indicates a significant risk of mobile dependency and addiction. Augner and Hacker (2012) identified young age as a major risk factor for problematic mobile phone use, along with female gender, chronic stress, low emotional stability, depression, and extraversion. Similarly, Csibi et al. (2021) found that young adults and preschool children are at the highest risk for smartphone-related addictive behaviors.

Mobile Phone Use and Academic Performance

The relationship between mobile phone use and academic performance has been widely researched. Many studies suggest a negative correlation. Ng et al. (2017) found that higher mobile phone use is associated with lower GPA among college students. Santhi and Rajesh (2020) reported that excessive smartphone use led to difficulties concentrating, poor study habits, and lower exam performance. Felisoni and Godoi (2018) also observed a negative correlation between smartphone usage during class and academic achievement. Kibona and Mgaya (2015) noted that combining mobile use with academic tasks reduced student productivity, with students reporting eye strain and overall academic decline.

According to Kaur (2018), while mobile phones have potential benefits in education, they are often distractions in the learning environment. Huey and Giguere (2022) echoed this, highlighting that smartphones divert attention from classroom activities and are often used more for entertainment than learning. In the Philippines, Buctot et al. (2021) found that nomophobia and smartphone addiction negatively impacted perceived academic performance (PAP). They noted that social media, gaming, and entertainment apps were major contributors to distractions and procrastination. Conversely, some studies have highlighted positive impacts. Zhao et al. (2018) found that students who used phones for educational purposes had higher academic performance based on cumulative GPA. Ozan (2013) also reported that mobile learning increased student interest and motivation. Lin et al. (2021) found that the use of phones for educational and news-related purposes positively influenced academic outcomes. Mobile devices are said to transform traditional learning methods into more innovative, interactive models (Kuzu, 2014, as cited in Demir & Akpınar, 2018; Middleton, 2015, as cited in Demir & Akpınar, 2018).

Abbasi et al. (2021) concluded that using smartphones for academic purposes could improve academic performance, though gaming remained a distraction. Chukwuere (2018) highlighted that students find smartphones useful for research and communication, though they also pose distractions. Shimray and Ramaiah (2019) noted that internet browsing had become routine, though with both academic and non-academic use. Troll et al. (2021) emphasized that the negative effects on academic performance depend more on how students manage smartphone usage rather than total screen time. Peteros et al. (2022) found that Filipino students maintained satisfactory academic performance even with frequent in-class smartphone use, noting only a slightly negative but statistically insignificant correlation between usage and achievement.

Mobile Phone Use and Quality of Life

Research has also focused on the impact of smartphone use on quality of life. Alotaibi et al. (2022) found that individuals addicted to smartphones exhibited lower GPA, physical inactivity, poor sleep, and discomfort in the neck, shoulders, and eyes. Olofinniyi et al. (2012) reported that people could spend up to nine hours daily on social media via mobile devices. Chen et al. (2020) found that using mobile phones solely for communication had no significant impact on overall well-being. However, Basu et al. (2018) noted that while individuals may attempt to reduce mobile usage, they often fail due to the devices' utility. Gomez (2024) compared prolonged smartphone use to gambling, suggesting potential behavioral alterations and mental health concerns. Similarly, Ratan et al. (2022) found associations between smartphone addiction and lower physical activity, insomnia, obesity, and risky behaviors like using phones while driving or eating.

Kim et al. (2017) supported these concerns, noting a higher risk of road accidents among mobile-dependent individuals. Nijboer et al. (2016) showed that multitasking with mobile phones impairs task performance. Silverman (2012) stated that smartphone addiction disrupts daily activities. Kamran et al. (2018) added that mobile use during meals can alter eating behavior. Winkler et al. (2020) further reported that problematic smartphone users experience stress, anxiety, depression, and physical discomfort. Daniyal et al. (2022) supported these findings, linking excessive phone use to physical and mental health issues. Sela et al. (2022) differentiated between "Aware" and "Unaware" usage modes, revealing that Unaware usage (i.e., unconscious, late-night usage) negatively impacts quality of life, especially emotional well-being, whereas Aware usage has a mildly positive effect. Chen et al. (2020) also found minimal differences in well-being between entertainment users and non-users, suggesting limited overall impact on life quality.

Research Gap

While numerous studies examine mobile dependence in relation to academic performance and quality of life individually, limited research explores all three variables together. In particular, few studies assess these relationships in a localized context. There is a notable gap in understanding how mobile dependence affects both academic success and well-being among tertiary students in the local context. Addressing this gap could yield valuable insights into the challenges these students face and help develop strategies for effective smartphone usage management.

Synthesis

The literature reveals the widespread and growing use of smartphones, especially among youth, and identifies both positive and negative impacts on academic performance and quality of life. While some studies highlight academic benefits from educational smartphone use, others point to distractions and lower productivity. Similarly, excessive usage is associated with adverse physical and mental health effects such as stress, poor sleep, and emotional instability.

Importantly, several studies note that the manner and purpose of smartphone use—not just duration—determine its impact. Conscious, intentional use appears less harmful, and may even be beneficial, while unconscious or excessive use poses greater risks. Lastly, this review underscores a critical gap in localized research that explores how mobile dependence impacts both academic performance and quality of life in specific student populations. Bridging this gap could help institutions develop effective interventions to guide healthy smartphone use among students.

Research Questions

This study aims to investigate the effect of mobile phone dependence on the academic performance and quality of life of tertiary level students. Specifically, the research seeks to answer the following questions:

1. How may the respondent be described as to:
 - 1.1 Age
 - 1.2 Sex
 - 1.3 College Department
 - 1.4 Year level
 - 1.5 Number of mobile phones
 - 1.6 Usual duration of mobile phone use
 - 1.7 Type of activities done using mobile phone, and
 - 1.8 General Weighted Average (AY 23-24 1st Sem)
2. What is the extent of mobile dependence of the respondents?
3. What is the level of quality of life of the respondents?
4. What is the difference of academic performance, mobile dependence, and quality of life of the respondents when grouped according to their demographic characteristics?
5. What is the relationship and effect of mobile dependence, academic performance, and quality of life of the respondents?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

A quantitative approach was utilized in this study. Particularly, this study made use of descriptive research design with comparative, correlational and predictive modeling (multi-method research design) to further understand the various effects of mobile dependence on academic performance and quality of life of tertiary students. By using descriptive research, the researchers can understand and identify the problem by looking at the characteristics of the problem (Siedlecki, 2019). Moreover, the study also aims to explore potential differences in mobile phone dependence, academic performance, and quality of life among tertiary level students when categorized by their demographics. Additionally, it seeks to determine the existence and strength of relationship and effect between mobile phone dependence, academic performance, and quality of life among these students. Mobile dependence, academic performance and quality of life will be

measured through the following specific variables: The assessment of mobile phone dependence will involve the use of the Smartphone Compulsion Questionnaire by Dr. David Greenfield. Academic performance will be evaluated based on the respondents' general weighted average. The measurement of quality of life will encompass their daily activities and overall life satisfaction, utilizing the World Health Organization Quality of Life Scale-Brief. All the information was gathered through survey research by face to face giving of the standardized questionnaires and will then be analyzed to test the hypothesis.

Respondents and Setting

A total of 342 students were targeted to participate in the data gathering conducted by the researchers from the total population of tertiary students in the university of 3061. This sample size was determined using the Raosoft software using the confidence level of 95% or the accepted margin of error of 5%. On another note, a total of 349 respondents participated during data collection. Inclusion criteria were as follows: (a.) a bonafide college student of the university, (b.) aged 18-59 years old, and (c.) are mobile phone users. The study was conducted within a Catholic tertiary level educational institution in San Fernando, Pampanga. Conducting the study within the university allowed for easy access of a diverse range of tertiary level students who fit the inclusion criteria.

Table 1. Computation of the sample size per college department.

College	Population	Proportion	Number of Respondents
Bachelor of Arts in Communication	82	.026	9
Bachelor of Elementary Education	85	.027	9
Bachelor in Human Services	24	.007	2
Bachelor of Science in Criminology	27	.009	3
Bachelor of Science in Hospitality Management	177	.058	20
Bachelor of Science in Psychology	147	.049	17
Bachelor of Science in Tourism Management	318	.104	36

Bachelor of Science in Accountancy	237	.077	27
Bachelor of Science in Accounting Information System	112	.037	13
Bachelor of Science in Architecture	279	.091	31
Bachelor of Science in Business Administration	349	.114	39
Bachelor of Science in Management	1	.0003	1
Bachelor of Science in Civil Engineering	293	.096	33
Bachelor of Science in Computer Engineering	52	.017	6
Bachelor of Secondary Education	20	.007	2
Bachelor of Science in Industrial Engineering	57	.017	6
Bachelor of Science in Information Technology	208	.068	23
Bachelor of Science in Nursing	509	.166	57
Bachelor of Science in Pharmacy	84	.027	9
TOTAL	3061	1	342

Sampling Method

The sampling design used in this study was stratified proportionate random sampling. Researchers employed stratified proportionate random sampling to diminish sampling bias and enhance the accuracy and relevance of their findings. This method enabled the researchers to consider the diversity within the population, leading to more reliable estimates of population characteristics. From the determined sample size of 342, the

researchers initially divided the population into strata based on their academic departments. Once the population is stratified, the researchers determined the proportion of respondents to be selected from each group based on its size relative to the total population as shown below in Table 1. Random sampling within each stratum was then conducted using random number generators in Microsoft Excel to ensure the selection process was truly random and representative of the entire population of students listed within each stratum.

Data Collection Procedure

1. The researchers sought approval from the respective deans of the colleges that will be involved in the study by submitting a formal letter for approval.
2. The researchers secured informed consent from the designated target respondents according to the specified inclusion criteria.
3. Upon obtaining their consent, hard copies of the questionnaires were distributed in person for dissemination. Each respondent received an identical copy of the questionnaire, which includes the study objectives, as well as questions designed to gather the required data for the study. The researchers provided detailed instructions on how to complete the questionnaires, which should take approximately 15- 20 minutes to answer.
4. After questionnaires are completed, they are collected from the respondents. Upon retrieval, the responses are tallied and evaluated to derive the results. The data gathered was stored by the focal person, the researchers and the concerned parties.

Research Instrument

The researchers prepared a survey questionnaire. The first part of the questionnaire, consisting of 10 items, inquired about the demographic information of the respondents including their a.) name (optional) b.) email address c.) age d.) sex e.) college department f.) year level g.) number of mobile phones h.) duration of mobile phone use i.) type of activities done in the mobile phone, and j.) GWA (AY 23-24 1st Sem) which also served as a measure of their academic performance. The second part, consisting of 15 items, measured mobile dependence of students through a Smartphone Compulsion Questionnaire, created by Dr. David Greenfield, a renowned psychologist and a world-known expert on technology addiction. The questions were designed to assess an individual's level of dependence on their smartphone usage. The questions addressed various aspects of smartphone use, including time spent on the device, behaviors associated with its use, feelings towards being without the smartphone, and its impact on daily activities. Respondents were asked to self-report their behaviors and attitudes related to smartphone usage. The third part, consisting of 29 items, measured the respondents' quality of life through the World Health Organization Quality of Life Scale-Brief, which consisted of questions assessing physical and environmental health, mental and emotional health, and spiritual and social health.

This instrument was done in consideration of the variables that were to be measured and included in the study to answer the research questions. The researchers selected

particular standardized questionnaires that measure mobile dependence and quality of life that fit the research design and scope of the study.

In order to have valid and reliable data, the researchers will also organize and arrange their survey questions in such a way that they will cover all areas of the study.

Data Analysis

Categorical variables were presented through frequency and percentage, accompanied by graphical representations in tables and charts. Quantitative variables were reported as mean \pm standard deviation (for normally distributed data) and as median with interquartile range (for non-normally distributed data).

To assess the relationship between continuous variables, Pearson product moment correlation was used. In addition, considering the potential presence or influence of confounders such as the demographic variables, regression analysis was employed.

Additionally, multivariate methods are used such as structural equation modeling (SEM) to examine the relationship between mobile phone dependence, academic performance (GWA), and quality of life (QoL) as latent constructs. This will allow pathways representing the direct effect of mobile dependence on academic performance and quality of life, as well as indirect effects mediated by other variables. SEM calculated the factor loadings which represents the strength of relationship between each observed variable and its underlying latent constructs.

Furthermore, comparison of mobile dependence, academic performance, and quality of life scores between two categorical levels of a variables (e.g. Sex) are done using t-test for independent samples (for normally distributed data) or Wilcoxon Mann-Whitney U test (for non-normally distributed data). For more than two categorical levels of a variable (e.g. Year level) Analysis of variance (ANOVA) were performed, for normally distributed data, otherwise Kruskal-Wallis test for non-normally distributed data.

To assess the fit of the regression model, assumptions checks of the linear regression were examined including assumptions for independence, normality, linearity and constancy of variance. Root mean square error was provided to assess the fit of the proposed SEM model. All statistical tests were conducted at a 5% level of significance (with Bonferroni corrections will be considered for multiple testing) using R studio software version 4.2.1.

Limitations of the Study

The study focused on the tertiary level students of a Catholic university in Pampanga for the school year of 2023- 2024. Students that participated from all levels and sections were involved. Overall there are 3061 students in total and 342 respondents were the target number of the population. This research study tackles the correlation of mobile dependence to the academic performance and quality of life of college students. Other

external factors that might affect mobile dependence, academic performance and quality of life of the students such as personality differences, personal challenges, leisure activities, psychological measurements, socioeconomic status, family dynamics, peer relationships, and study habits were not considered.

RESULTS

The collected data was arranged, totaled, and examined in accordance with the objectives of the study. Both textual and tabular presentations of the collected data were made.

In total, there were 349 respondents in the study, predominantly young adults with an average age of 20.23 years (SD = 1.478) and exhibit high academic performance with an average general weighted average (GWA) of 87.59 (SD = 4.506). The sample also comprised 57.31% males (n = 200) and 42.69% females (n = 149). Notably, the most represented courses are Bachelor of Science in Nursing with 15.76% (n = 55) and Bachelor of Science in Architecture with 11.75% (n = 41). In terms of academic standing, 35.53% (n = 124) are in their first year, followed by 25.79% (n = 90) in their second year, 22.06% (n = 77) in their third year, and 16.62% (n = 58) in their fourth year. The majority of respondents (79.94%, n = 279) own one device, with a significant portion (42.69%, n = 149) using their devices for 7-10 hours daily. The primary activities include internet search/web browsing (90.26%, n = 315), entertainment (89.40%, n = 312), and communication (89.11%, n = 311). Furthermore, 81.95% (n = 286) use devices for academic purposes, while 72.78% (n = 254) engage in online shopping, and 62.18% (n = 217) participate in gaming.

Table 2. Demographic characteristics of the respondents.

	M	SD
Age	20.23	1.478
General weighted average	87.59	4.506
	n	%
Sex		
Male	200	57.31
Female	149	42.69
Course		
Bachelor in Human Services	3	0.86
Bachelor of Arts in Communication	7	2.01
Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEEEd)	11	3.15
Bachelor of Science in Accountancy	28	8.02
Bachelor of Science in Accounting Information Systems	13	3.72
Bachelor of Science in Architecture	41	11.75
Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Marketing	35	10.03
Bachelor of Science in Business Administration Marketing	1	0.29

Bachelor of Science in Civil Engineering	32	9.17
Bachelor of Science in Computer Engineering	7	2.01
Bachelor of Science in Criminology	3	0.86
Bachelor of Science in Hospitality Management	20	5.73
Bachelor of Science in Industrial Engineering	6	1.72
Bachelor of Science in Information Technology	23	6.59
Bachelor of Science in Nursing	55	15.76
Bachelor of Science in Pharmacy	10	2.87
Bachelor of Science in Psychology	19	5.44
Bachelor of Science in Tourism Management (BSTM)	33	9.46
Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSEd)	2	0.57
Year Level		
Level I	124	35.53
Level II	90	25.79
Level III	77	22.06
Level IV	58	16.62
Number of devices		
1	279	79.94
2	56	16.05
3	12	3.44
4	2	0.57
Duration of device use		
1-2 hours	32	9.17
3-6 hours	96	27.51
7-10 hours	149	42.69
11-15 hours	54	15.47
16-20 hours	16	4.58
more than 20 hours	2	0.57
Type of activity		
Internet search/web browsing	315	90.26
Entertainment	312	89.40
Communication	311	89.11
Academic/learning purpose	286	81.95
Buying products/online shopping	254	72.78
Gaming	217	62.18

Table 3.1. revealed the results of the smartphone compulsion test among respondents, with 87.68% (n = 306) admitting they spend more time on their cell or smartphone than they realize, and 88.83% (n = 310) regularly passing time mindlessly on these devices. A notable 75.64% (n = 264) often lose track of time when using their phones. Over half of the respondents (60.17%, n = 210) prefer texting, tweeting, or emailing over in-person conversations. The increasing trend in smartphone usage is acknowledged by 71.63% (n = 250), while 78.80% (n = 275) wish they could be less involved with their phones. Regularly sleeping with their phone nearby is common for 58.45% (n = 204) of respondents, and 63.90% (n = 223) check messages at all hours, even when it interrupts

other activities. Alarming, 54.15% (n = 189) use their phones while driving or during activities that require concentration. Productivity concerns are noted by 79.66% (n = 278), and 68.19% (n = 238) feel uneasy without their phones. The discomfort of being without their phone is echoed by 78.80% (n = 275), and for 72.21% (n = 252), their phone is a regular part of meal settings. Additionally, 73.07% (n = 255) feel an intense urge to check notifications when their phone signals, and 75.64% (n = 264) mindlessly check their phones many times a day.

Table 3.1. Frequency distribution of smartphone compulsion test per item.

	n	%
1. Do you find yourself spending more time on your cell or smartphone than you realize?		
Yes	306	87.68
No	43	12.32
2. Do you find yourself mindlessly passing time regularly by staring at your cell or smartphone?		
Yes	310	88.83
No	39	11.17
3. Do you seem to lose track of time when on your cell or smartphone?		
Yes	264	75.64
No	85	24.36
4. Do you find yourself spending more time texting, tweeting, or emailing as opposed to talking to people in person?		
Yes	210	60.17
No	139	39.83
5. Has the amount of time you spend on your cell or smartphone been increasing?		
Yes	250	71.63
No	99	28.37
6. Do you wish you could be a little less involved with your phone?		
Yes	275	78.80
No	74	21.20
7. Do you sleep with your cell or smartphone (turned on) under your pillow or next to your bed on a regular basis?		
Yes	204	58.45
No	45	41.55
8. Do you find yourself viewing and answering texts, tweets, and emails at all hours of the day and night—even if it means interrupting other things you are doing?		
Yes	223	63.90
No	126	36.10
9. Do you text, email, tweet, Snapchat, Facebook message, or surf while driving or doing other similar activities that require your focused attention and concentration?		
Yes	189	54.15
No	160	45.85

10. Do you feel your use of your cell or smartphone decreases your productivity at times?		
Yes	278	79.66
No	71	20.34
11. Do you feel reluctant to be without your cell or smartphone, even for a short time?		
Yes	238	68.19
No	111	31.81
12. Do you feel ill at ease or uncomfortable when you accidentally leave your smartphone in the car or at home, have no service, or have a broken phone?		
Yes	275	78.80
No	74	21.20
13. When you eat meals, is your cell or smartphone always part of the table place setting?		
Yes	252	72.21
No	97	27.79
14. When your cell or smartphone rings, beeps, or buzzes, do you feel an intense urge to check for texts, tweets, emails, updates, and so on?		
Yes	255	73.07
No	94	26.93
15. Do you find yourself mindlessly checking your cell or smartphone many times a day, even when you know there is likely nothing new or important to see?		
Yes	264	75.64
No	85	24.36

Table 3.2 shows the overall mobile dependence score among respondents. The average overall mobile dependence score among respondents was 10.87 (SD = 3.088). According to the criteria set by *Dr. David Greenfield, Center for Internet and Technology Addiction*, this indicates that, on average, respondents might want to consider seeing a psychologist, psychiatrist, or psychotherapist who specializes in behavioral addictions for a consultation.

Table 3.2. Overall mobile dependence score among respondents.

	n	%
1-2: Normal	2	0.57
3-4: Leaning toward problematic or compulsive use	10	2.87
5 or above: May have a problematic or compulsive smartphone use	40	11.46
8 or higher: Might consider for a consult	297	85.10
	M	SD
Average smartphone compulsion score	10.87	3.088

Table 4.1 shows the overall quality of life and general health rating among respondents. The survey results reveal that the average overall quality of life and general health rating among respondents is 7.27 (SD = 1.292). When asked to rate their quality of life, the majority expressed positive sentiments, with 54.44% (n = 190) feeling satisfied and

12.89% (n = 45) feeling very satisfied. Conversely, only a small fraction reported negative perceptions, with 0.86% (n = 3) rating their quality of life as very poor and 2.01% (n = 7) rating it as poor. A significant portion of respondents, 29.80% (n = 104), rated their quality of life as neither poor nor good. Regarding health satisfaction, 45.56% (n = 159) of respondents reported being satisfied with their health, and 7.45% (n = 26) felt very satisfied. However, some respondents were less positive, with 1.43% (n = 5) rating their health as very poor and 6.88% (n = 24) as poor. A notable 38.68% (n = 135) felt neutral, rating their health as neither poor nor good.

Table 4.1. Overall quality of life and general health.

	M	SD
Average overall quality of life and general health	7.27	1.292
	n	%
1. How would you rate your quality of life?		
Very poor	3	0.86
Poor	7	2.01
Neither poor nor good	104	29.80
Satisfied	190	54.44
Very satisfied	45	12.89
2. How satisfied are you with your health?		
Very poor	5	1.43
Poor	24	6.88
Neither poor nor good	135	38.68
Satisfied	159	45.56
Very satisfied	26	7.45

Table 4.2 presents the respondents' physical health domain scores. The physical health domain presented below reveals an average physical health score of 22.99 (SD = 3.456) and an average transformed scale score of 57.37 (SD = 12.530). Regarding the extent to which physical pain prevents respondents from performing necessary tasks, 46.70% (n = 163) report a moderate amount of pain, while 28.08% (n = 98) experience a little pain, and 13.75% (n = 48) are very much affected. A smaller proportion reports not being affected at all (3.44%, n = 12) or being extremely affected (8.02%, n = 28). When asked about the need for medical treatment to function, 38.68% (n = 135) indicate a moderate need, followed by 23.21% (n = 81) expressing a high need, and 16.05% (n = 56) an extreme need. Conversely, 16.91% (n = 59) need a little treatment, and 5.16% (n = 18) do not need treatment at all. Energy levels for everyday life are reported as moderate by 47.28% (n = 165) of respondents, mostly adequate by 32.09% (n = 112), and completely sufficient by 7.16% (n = 25), while 11.75% (n = 41) have a little energy, and 1.72% (n = 6) have none. Mobility is generally satisfactory, with 44.99% (n = 157) satisfied and 9.46% (n = 33) very satisfied, while 41.83% (n = 146) report neutral satisfaction. Regarding sleep, 27.79% (n = 97) are satisfied, and 4.30% (n = 15) very satisfied, whereas 20.34% (n = 71) are dissatisfied, and 6.02% (n = 21) very dissatisfied. When it comes to performing daily living activities, 35.82% (n = 125) are satisfied, 9.46% (n = 33) very

satisfied, and 43.84% (n = 153) are neutral, with 9.46% (n = 33) dissatisfied and 1.43% (n = 5) very dissatisfied. Lastly, satisfaction with the capacity for work shows 34.67% (n = 121) satisfied and 7.16% (n = 25) very satisfied, while 49.57% (n = 173) are neutral, and 7.74% (n = 27) dissatisfied, with only 0.86% (n = 3) very dissatisfied.

Table 4.2. Physical health domain

	M	SD
Average Physical health score	22.99	3.456
Average Physical health transformed scale score	57.37	12.530
	n	%
3. To what extent do you feel that physical pain prevents you from doing what you need to do?		
Not at all	12	3.44
A little	98	28.08
A moderate amount	163	46.70
Very much	48	13.75
An extreme	28	8.02
4. How much do you need any medical treatment to function in your life?		
Not at all	18	5.16
A little	59	16.91
A moderate amount	135	38.68
Very much	81	23.21
An extreme	56	16.05
10. Do you have enough energy for everyday life?		
Not at all	6	1.72
A little	41	11.75
Moderately	165	47.28
Mostly	112	32.09
Completely	25	7.16
15. How well are you able to get around?		
Very poor	3	0.86
Poor	10	2.87
Neither poor nor good	146	41.83
Satisfied	157	44.99
Very satisfied	33	9.46
16. How satisfied are you with your sleep?		
Very dissatisfied	21	6.02
Dissatisfied	71	20.34
Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied	145	41.55
Satisfied	97	27.79
Very satisfied	15	4.30
17. How satisfied are you with your ability to perform your daily living activities?		
Very dissatisfied	5	1.43

Dissatisfied	33	9.46
Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied	153	43.84
Satisfied	125	35.82
Very satisfied	33	9.46
18. How satisfied are you with your capacity for work?		
Very dissatisfied	3	0.86
Dissatisfied	27	7.74
Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied	173	49.57
Satisfied	121	34.67
Very satisfied	25	7.16

Table 4.3 presents the respondents' scores in the psychological domain. The psychological domain of the respondents reveals an average psychological score of 20.60 (SD = 3.485) and an average psychological transformed scale score of 61.08 (SD = 14.630). When asked about life enjoyment, 47.28% (n = 165) reported enjoying life very much, while 20.63% (n = 72) enjoyed it to an extreme extent. Regarding the meaningfulness of life, 42.12% (n = 147) felt their life was very meaningful, and 35.24% (n = 123) felt it was moderately meaningful. Concentration levels were mostly moderate, with 54.15% (n = 189) reporting moderate concentration and 32.09% (n = 112) mostly able to concentrate. When it comes to body image acceptance, 40.69% (n = 142) accepted their bodily appearance moderately, and 31.52% (n = 110) mostly accepted it. In terms of self-satisfaction, 38.11% (n = 133) were neither satisfied nor dissatisfied, while 35.82% (n = 125) were satisfied. Negative feelings were quite common, with 37.82% (n = 132) experiencing them quite often and 28.37% (n = 99) very often.

Table 4.3. Psychological domain

	M	SD
Average Psychological score	20.60	3.485
Average Psychological transformed scale score	61.08	14.630
	n	%
5. How much do you enjoy life?		
Not at all	4	1.15
A little	19	5.44
A moderate amount	89	25.50
Very much	165	47.28
An extreme	72	20.63
6. To what extent do you feel your life to be meaningful?		
Not at all	3	0.86
A little	15	4.30
A moderate amount	123	35.24
Very much	147	42.12
An extreme	61	17.48
7. How well are you able to concentrate?		
Not at all	4	1.15

A little	28	8.02
Moderately	189	54.15
Mostly	112	32.09
Completely	16	4.58
11. Are you able to accept your bodily appearance?		
Not at all	14	4.01
A little	41	11.75
Moderately	142	40.69
Mostly	110	31.52
Completely	42	12.03
19. How satisfied are you with yourself?		
Very dissatisfied	9	2.58
Dissatisfied	31	8.88
Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied	133	38.11
Satisfied	125	35.82
Very satisfied	51	14.61
26. How often do you have negative feelings, such as blue mood, despair, anxiety, depression?		
Never	31	8.88
Seldom	81	23.21
Quite often	132	37.82
Very often	99	28.37
Always	6	1.72

Table 4.4 presents the respondents' scores in the social relationships domain. The average social relationships score among the respondents is 10.92 (SD = 2.270), with the transformed scale score averaging 66.03 (SD = 19.137). Satisfaction with personal relationships shows that 42.69% (n = 149) are satisfied and 18.91% (n = 66) are very satisfied, while 30.37% (n = 106) are neutral, and a smaller portion are dissatisfied (6.59%, n = 23) or very dissatisfied (1.43%, n = 5). Regarding satisfaction with their sex life, 36.68% (n = 128) are neutral, 24.93% (n = 87) are satisfied, and 17.19% (n = 60) are very satisfied. Conversely, 17.19% (n = 60) are very dissatisfied, and 4.01% (n = 14) are dissatisfied. When it comes to support from friends, 37.82% (n = 132) of respondents are satisfied, and 34.38% (n = 120) are very satisfied, while 23.50% (n = 82) are neutral. Only a small percentage are dissatisfied (2.87%, n = 10) or very dissatisfied (0.86%, n = 3).

Table 4.4. Social relationships domain

	M	SD
Average Social relationships score	10.92	2.270
Average Social relationships transformed scale score	66.03	19.137
	n	%
20. How satisfied are you with your personal relationships?		
Very dissatisfied	5	1.43
Dissatisfied	23	6.59

Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied	106	30.37
Satisfied	149	42.69
Very satisfied	66	18.91
21. How satisfied are you with your sex life?		
Very dissatisfied	60	17.19
Dissatisfied	14	4.01
Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied	128	36.68
Satisfied	87	24.93
Very satisfied	60	17.19
22. How satisfied are you with the support you get from your friends?		
Very dissatisfied	3	0.86
Dissatisfied	10	2.87
Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied	82	23.50
Satisfied	132	37.82
Very satisfied	120	34.38

Table 4.5 presents the respondents' scores in the environment domain. The environmental domain scores reflect the respondents' perceptions of their surroundings, with an average environment score of 28.48 (SD = 4.175) and an average transformed scale score of 65.64 (SD = 13.205). Regarding safety, 42.98% (n = 150) of respondents feel very safe, while 42.41% (n = 148) feel moderately safe. The physical environment is considered very healthy by 37.54% (n = 131) and moderately healthy by 41.83% (n = 146). Financial adequacy to meet daily needs is reported as moderate by 38.40% (n = 134) and mostly adequate by 37.54% (n = 131). Information availability in daily life is mostly sufficient for 43.55% (n = 152) and moderately sufficient for 38.11% (n = 133). Leisure opportunities are moderately available to 45.27% (n = 158) and mostly available to 40.11% (n = 140). Satisfaction with living conditions shows that 42.12% (n = 147) are satisfied, and 28.08% (n = 98) are neutral. Access to health services satisfies 42.69% (n = 149) of respondents, with 36.68% (n = 128) feeling neutral. Lastly, 31.81% (n = 111) are satisfied with their mode of transportation, while 43.84% (n = 153) are neutral.

Table 4.5. Environment domain

	M	SD
Average Environment score	28.48	4.175
Average Environment transformed scale score	65.64	13.205
	n	%
8. How safe do you feel in your daily life?		
Not at all	1	0.29
Slightly	15	4.30
A moderate amount	148	42.41
Very much	150	42.98
Extremely	35	10.03
9. How healthy is your physical environment?		

Not at all	2	0.57
Slightly	35	10.03
A moderate amount	146	41.83
Very much	131	37.54
Extremely	35	10.03
12. Do you have enough money to meet your needs?		
Not at all	11	3.15
A little	32	9.17
Moderately	134	38.40
Mostly	131	37.54
Completely	41	11.75
13. How available to you is the information that you need in your day-to-day life?		
Not at all	0	0.00
A little	15	4.30
Moderately	133	38.11
Mostly	152	43.55
Completely	49	14.04
14. To what extent do you have the opportunity for leisure activities?		
Not at all	5	1.43
A little	20	5.73
Moderately	158	45.27
Mostly	140	40.11
Completely	26	7.45
23. How satisfied are you with the conditions of your living place?		
Very dissatisfied	1	0.29
Dissatisfied	12	3.44
Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied	98	28.08
Satisfied	147	42.12
Very satisfied	91	26.07
24. How satisfied are you with your access to health services?		
Very dissatisfied	2	0.57
Dissatisfied	23	6.59
Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied	128	36.68
Satisfied	149	42.69
Very satisfied	47	13.47
25. How satisfied are you with your mode of transportation?		
Very dissatisfied	9	2.58
Dissatisfied	45	12.89
Neither satisfied nor dissatisfied	153	43.84
Satisfied	111	31.81
Very satisfied	31	8.88

Table 5.1 presents the comparison between males and females on various measures and reveals some noteworthy differences and similarities. In terms of the General Weighted Average (GWA), females have a slightly higher mean ($M = 87.90$, $SD = 4.64$) compared to males ($M = 87.18$, $SD = 4.30$), although this difference is not statistically significant ($t = 1.49$, $p = 0.137$). Similarly, for the Mobile Dependence Score, females score higher ($M = 11.06$, $SD = 3.09$) than males ($M = 10.61$, $SD = 3.07$), but again the difference is not significant ($t = 1.35$, $p = 0.179$). When evaluating Quality of Life, the overall quality of life and general health scores are nearly identical between females ($M = 7.32$, $SD = 1.23$) and males ($M = 7.21$, $SD = 1.38$) with no significant difference ($t = 0.72$, $p = 0.474$). However, significant differences are found in physical health and psychological well-being. Males report higher physical health scores ($M = 59.72$, $SD = 13.60$) compared to females ($M = 55.62$, $SD = 11.40$), with this difference being statistically significant ($t = -3.06$, $p = 0.002$). Similarly, males have higher psychological well-being scores ($M = 63.66$, $SD = 14.90$) than females ($M = 59.15$, $SD = 14.20$), also showing a significant difference ($t = -2.88$, $p = 0.004$). In terms of social relations, both sexes have comparable scores (males: $M = 65.46$, $SD = 20.00$; females: $M = 66.45$, $SD = 18.50$) with no significant difference ($t = 0.48$, $p = 0.634$). Lastly, males have higher scores in the environmental domain ($M = 67.34$, $SD = 13.60$) compared to females ($M = 64.38$, $SD = 12.80$), and this difference is statistically significant ($t = -2.08$, $p = 0.038$).

Table 5.1. Comparison between sex on the General weighted average, mobile dependence, and Quality of life

	Male		Female		<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>		
General weighted average	87.18	4.30	87.90	4.64	1.49	0.137
Mobile dependence score	10.61	3.07	11.06	3.09	1.35	0.179
Quality of life						
Overall quality of life and general health	7.21	1.38	7.32	1.23	0.72	0.474
Physical health	59.72	13.60	55.62	11.40	-3.06	0.002
Psychological	63.66	14.90	59.15	14.20	-2.88	0.004
Social relations	65.46	20.00	66.45	18.50	0.48	0.634
Environment	67.34	13.60	64.38	12.80	-2.08	0.038

Table 5.2 presents the results of ANOVA analyses comparing various metrics among different colleges. The results indicate a significant difference in the general weighted average among the colleges ($F = 35.35$, $p < 0.001$). The college with the highest average is the IT college ($M = 90.70$, $SD = 2.94$), while the college with the lowest average is the CEA ($M = 84.20$, $SD = 3.94$). There is no significant difference in mobile dependence scores among the colleges ($F = 0.165$, $p = 0.685$). The scores range from a mean of 9.38 ($SD = 3.64$) in the EDUC college to a mean of 12.20 ($SD = 3.01$) in the SBPA college. The overall quality of life and general health scores do not differ significantly among the colleges ($F = 1.601$, $p = 0.207$). Scores range from a mean of 6.75 ($SD = 1.24$) in the SAS college to a mean of 7.57 ($SD = 1.17$) in the CONP college.

Table 5.2. Comparison among Colleges on the General weighted average, mobile dependence, and Quality of life

		CONP		CEA		SBPA		SAS		EDUC		CHTM		IT		ACCOUNT		F-value	p	
		M	SD	M	SD															
General weighted average		87.10	3.57	84.20	3.94	88.60	6.62	90.20	3.86	89.10	2.66	89.40	3.17	90.70	2.94	88.10	3.10	3.39	35.35	<0.001
Mobile dependence score		10.50	3.25	10.60	2.78	12.20	3.01	11.80	2.79	9.38	3.64	11.70	2.92	10.20	3.01	9.90	3.90	3.15	0.165	0.685
Quality of life																				
Overall quality of life and general health		7.57	1.17	6.91	1.25	7.36	1.20	6.75	1.24	7.23	1.59	7.53	1.28	7.48	1.08	7.46	1.48	1.48	1.601	0.207
Physical health		57.80	12.60	53.90	11.30	64.70	11.70	53.90	12.00	60.70	6.14	57.50	11.20	59.90	15.10	57.60	14.80	0.797	0.373	
Psychological		62.90	15.50	59.20	14.40	61.00	10.70	52.00	15.90	65.90	12.70	62.40	13.90	64.20	14.60	64.20	14.80	1.801	0.180	
Social relations		67.30	16.80	57.60	20.30	68.20	16.90	68.60	16.70	72.50	15.10	67.90	20.90	73.40	17.80	69.10	19.00	7.957	0.005	
Environment		68.90	13.10	61.00	11.40	65.00	11.00	60.10	12.60	70.80	10.40	67.90	15.10	69.00	12.30	68.70	14.40	4.162	0.042	

Table 5.3 presents the comparison of year-level categories and reveals significant differences in General Weighted Average (GWA) among students, with first-year students (Level I) having the highest average GWA of 88.90 (SD = 4.01) and fourth-year students (Level IV) having the lowest average GWA of 85.30 (SD = 4.13), resulting in an F-value of 11.010 and a p-value of less than 0.001, indicating a statistically significant difference. In contrast, the Mobile Dependence Score shows no significant variation across year levels, with averages ranging from 10.40 (SD = 3.56) in third-year students (Level III) to 11.00 (SD = 2.97) in both first-year and second-year students (Level I and II), yielding an F-value of 0.684 and a p-value of 0.562. The overall Quality of Life and General Health scores are relatively similar across all year levels, with first-year students averaging 7.23 (SD = 1.27) and third-year students averaging 7.44 (SD = 1.34), showing an F-value of 1.245 and a p-value of 0.293. The Physical Health scores also do not differ significantly, with third-year students having the highest average of 59.40 (SD = 13.80) and fourth-year students the lowest at 54.70 (SD = 11.60), resulting in an F-value of 1.685 and a p-value of 0.170. Similarly, Psychological scores are fairly consistent, ranging from 60.30 (SD =

14.90) in fourth-year students to 62.50 (SD = 15.90) in third-year students, with an F-value of 0.391 and a p-value of 0.760. Social Relations scores show more variability, with second-year students averaging 68.30 (SD = 19.50) and fourth-year students 60.30 (SD = 17.80), but this difference is not statistically significant (F-value = 2.312, p-value = 0.076). Finally, the Environment scores range from 62.60 (SD = 13.00) in fourth-year students to 67.30 (SD = 13.70) in both second and third-year students, with an F-value of 2.085 and a p-value of 0.102.

Table 5.3. Comparison among year-level categories on the General weighted average, mobile dependence, and Quality of life

	Level I		Level II		Level III		Level IV		F-value	p
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD		
General weighted average	88.90	4.01	88.10	3.95	86.60	5.27	85.30	4.13	11.010	<0.001
Mobile dependence score	11.00	2.97	11.00	2.94	10.40	3.56	10.90	2.91	0.684	0.562
Quality of life										
Overall quality of life and general health	7.23	1.27	7.34	1.26	7.44	1.34	7.03	1.30	1.245	0.293
Physical health	57.80	12.20	56.80	12.20	59.40	13.80	54.70	11.60	1.685	0.170
Psychological	60.40	14.30	61.30	13.90	62.50	15.90	60.30	14.90	0.391	0.760
Social relations	66.10	19.20	68.30	19.50	67.40	19.00	60.30	17.80	2.312	0.076
Environment	64.80	12.70	67.30	13.30	67.30	13.70	62.60	13.00	2.085	0.102

Table 5.4. presents a comparison of various outcome measures among respondent categories based on the number of devices owned. The mean general weighted average (GWA) across categories ranges from 83.70 to 88.50, with no significant difference observed (F = 1.027, p = 0.312). Similarly, the mobile dependence score exhibits minimal variation across categories, ranging from 10.60 to 12.50 (F = 0.042, p = 0.838). Regarding quality of life dimensions, no significant differences emerge in overall quality of life and general health (F = 1.805, p = 0.180), physical health (F = 0.309, p = 0.579), psychological well-being (F = 0.092, p = 0.762), or social relations (F = 0.318, p = 0.573), as well as in the environmental quality of life dimension (F = 0.001, p = 0.973).

Table 5.4. Comparison among the number of devices owned among respondent categories on the General weighted average, mobile dependence, and Quality of life

	One		Two		Three		Four		F-value	p
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD		
General weighted average	87.60	4.20	88.50	4.02	83.70	9.76	87.00	1.34	1.027	0.312
Mobile dependence score	10.90	3.22	10.60	2.43	11.40	2.64	12.50	3.54	0.042	0.838
Quality of life										

Overall quality of life and general health	7.29	1.26	7.38	1.36	6.75	1.48	5.50	0.71	1.805	0.180
Physical health	57.30	12.90	57.00	10.80	60.60	11.90	59.50	21.90	0.309	0.579
Psychological	61.20	14.70	60.00	13.90	68.30	12.70	34.50	13.40	0.092	0.762
Social relations	65.80	19.10	66.30	18.10	70.80	25.60	62.50	17.70	0.318	0.573
Environment	65.50	13.40	67.10	12.40	63.70	12.90	59.50	4.95	0.001	0.973

Table 5.5 presents the comparison of various outcomes across different durations of device use categories. In terms of GWA, there is a slight increase from 87.30 (SD = 4.12) for 1-2 hours of use to 91.90 (SD = 6.36) for more than 20 hours of use, although the overall difference is not statistically significant ($F = 1.147$, $p = 0.285$). However, regarding mobile dependence, there is a significant difference observed ($F = 7.020$, $p = 0.008$), with scores ranging from 10.40 (SD = 3.67) for 1-2 hours of use to 10.50 (SD = 0.71) for more than 20 hours of use. Quality of life measures varied across different domains. While overall QoL and general health scores showed significant differences ($F = 4.810$, $p = 0.029$), with the highest scores observed for 3-6 hours of use (7.57, SD = 1.34), physical health and social relation scores did not vary significantly across groups ($F = 0.026$, $p = 0.873$ and $F = 0.776$, $p = 0.379$ respectively). However, psychological and environmental scores varied significantly, with the highest scores observed for 3-6 hours of use (63.70, SD = 13.40). Social relations and environmental QoL scores also showed significant variations ($F = 7.871$, $p = 0.005$ and $F = 9.223$, $p = 0.003$ respectively).

Table 5.5. Comparison among the duration of device use categories on the General weighted average, mobile dependence, and Quality of life

	1-2 hours		3-6 hours		7-10 hours		11-15 hours		16-20 hours		more than 20 hours		F-value	p
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD		
General weighted average	87.30	4.12	87.70	5.11	87.30	4.36	87.70	4.29	89.10	3.08	91.90	6.36	1.147	0.285
Mobile dependence score	10.40	3.67	10.00	3.26	11.20	2.83	11.40	3.04	11.40	2.56	10.50	0.71	7.020	0.008
Quality of life														
Overall quality of life and general health	7.44	1.08	7.57	1.34	7.09	1.28	7.26	1.28	6.94	1.34	7.00	1.41	4.810	0.029
Physical health	55.70	10.00	58.60	12.20	56.50	13.40	58.60	12.80	57.20	10.70	56.00	0.00	0.026	0.873
Psychological	63.60	13.50	63.70	13.40	60.80	15.20	57.50	14.40	55.90	16.00	53.50	21.90	9.223	0.003
Social relations	62.10	19.60	68.70	17.10	63.60	19.90	67.80	17.00	75.50	25.20	53.00	4.24	0.776	0.379
Environment	65.10	12.80	70.20	12.80	64.00	12.90	64.00	13.60	62.00	11.90	53.50	21.90	7.871	0.005

Tables 5.6.1-5.6.6 present the results of t-tests comparing various outcomes (general weighted average, mobile dependence score, and different aspects of quality of life) between groups of individuals who use their mobile phones for specific purposes and those who do not. The comparison of mobile phone use for academic/learning purposes

revealed a significant difference in the general weighted average between users and non-users. Individuals who used their mobile phones for academic or learning purposes had a lower general weighted average ($M = 87.31$, $SD = 4.64$) compared to those who did not ($M = 88.87$, $SD = 3.61$), with a t -value of -2.51 and a p -value of 0.012 . For internet search and web browsing, there were no significant differences in the general weighted average, mobile dependence score, or any aspects of quality of life between users and non-users. The p -values for all comparisons were greater than 0.05 , indicating no significant impact of mobile phone use for this purpose on the measured outcomes. Similarly, the use of mobile phones for entertainment did not show any significant differences in the general weighted average, mobile dependence score, or quality of life measures between users and non-users. All p -values exceeded 0.05 , suggesting no notable effects of entertainment use on these outcomes. The results also showed no significant differences in the general weighted average, mobile dependence score, or quality of life aspects for those using mobile phones for communication compared to those who did not. The p -values were all above 0.05 , indicating no significant impact from using mobile phones for communication purposes. The comparison for buying products or online shopping purposes did not yield any significant differences in the general weighted average, mobile dependence score, or quality of life measures. Again, all p -values were above 0.05 , suggesting no significant effects from using mobile phones for online shopping. Lastly, the use of mobile phones for gaming purposes did not show significant differences in the general weighted average, mobile dependence score, or quality of life measures between users and non-users. All p -values were greater than 0.05 , indicating no notable impact of gaming use on the measured outcomes.

Table 5.6.1 Comparison between Use of mobile on Internet search/web browsing on the General weight average, mobile dependence, and Quality of life

	Yes		No		<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>		
General weighted average	87.48	4.60	88.65	3.35	-1.43	0.151
Mobile dependence score	10.82	3.06	11.29	3.34	-0.84	0.398
Quality of life						
Overall quality of life and general health	7.25	1.32	7.44	0.96	-0.80	0.423
Physical health	57.62	12.60	55.12	11.60	1.11	0.270
Psychological	61.05	14.90	61.32	11.90	-0.10	0.918
Social relations	66.21	19.00	64.32	20.30	0.55	0.585
Environment	66.03	13.40	62.06	11.10	1.67	0.096

Table 5.6.2 Comparison between Use of mobile on Entertainment on the General weighted average, mobile dependence, and Quality of life

	Yes		No		<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>		
General weighted average	87.58	4.66	87.73	2.94	-0.20	0.841

Mobile dependence score	10.86	3.05	10.97	3.40	-0.22	0.828
Quality of life						
Overall quality of life and general health	7.29	1.28	7.16	1.42	0.55	0.585
Physical health	57.49	12.70	56.35	10.80	0.52	0.600
Psychological	60.98	14.80	61.92	13.20	-0.37	0.712
Social relations	65.97	19.40	66.51	17.00	-0.16	0.871
Environment	65.68	13.30	65.35	12.40	0.14	0.887

Table 5.6.3 Comparison between Use of mobile on Communication on the General weighted average, mobile dependence, and Quality of life.

	Yes		No		<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>		
General weighted average	87.53	4.65	88.14	3.12	-0.79	0.429
Mobile dependence score	10.80	3.07	11.45	3.18	-1.23	0.221
Quality of life						
Overall quality of life and general health	7.28	1.31	7.18	1.11	0.44	0.657
Physical health	57.55	12.70	55.92	11.10	0.76	0.450
Psychological	61.17	14.70	60.29	13.80	0.35	0.726
Social relations	66.67	18.90	60.82	20.70	1.78	0.075
Environment	65.91	13.30	63.47	12.40	1.07	0.284

Table 5.6.4 Comparison between Use of mobile on Academic/learning purpose on the General weighted average, mobile dependence, and Quality of life

	Yes		No		<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>		
General weighted average	87.31	4.64	88.87	3.61	-2.51	0.012
Mobile dependence score	10.74	3.13	11.46	2.82	-1.69	0.092
Quality of life						
Overall quality of life and general health	7.31	1.25	7.08	1.48	1.31	0.191
Physical health	57.79	12.80	55.48	11.00	1.33	0.185
Psychological	61.22	14.90	60.43	13.60	0.39	0.698
Social relations	65.87	19.10	66.75	19.50	-0.33	0.743
Environment	65.64	13.30	65.65	13.00	-0.004	0.997

Table 5.6.5 Comparison between Use of mobile on Buying products/Online shopping purpose on the General weighted average, mobile dependence, and Quality of life

	Yes		No		<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>		
General weighted average	87.67	4.70	87.37	3.97	0.55	0.581
Mobile dependence score	10.89	3.02	10.80	3.27	0.25	0.801
Quality of life						
Overall quality of life and general health	7.32	1.29	7.14	1.28	1.20	0.232
Physical health	57.57	12.60	56.85	12.40	0.47	0.636
Psychological	61.57	14.70	59.76	14.30	1.03	0.304
Social relations	67.06	18.30	63.26	21.10	1.66	0.099
Environment	66.16	13.50	64.26	12.30	1.20	0.233

Table 5.6.6 Comparison between Use of mobile on Gaming purpose on the General weighted average, mobile dependence, and Quality of life

	Yes		No		<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>		
General weighted average	87.33	4.20	88.02	4.95	-1.39	0.167
Mobile dependence score	11.00	2.98	10.66	3.26	0.99	0.324
Quality of life						
Overall quality of life and general health	7.33	1.27	7.17	1.32	1.10	0.270
Physical health	57.68	12.90	56.87	12.00	0.58	0.561
Psychological	61.43	14.90	60.50	14.20	0.57	0.566
Social relations	64.59	18.90	68.40	19.30	-1.81	0.071
Environment	65.93	13.60	65.18	12.60	0.51	0.610

Table 5.7 compares the general weighted average, mobile dependence, and various aspects of quality of life between two age categories: individuals younger than 20 years old and those older than 20 years old. The general weighted average is significantly higher for individuals younger than 20 years old ($M = 88.51$, $SD = 3.85$) compared to those older than 20 years old ($M = 86.18$, $SD = 5.06$), with a t -value of 4.88 and a p -value of less than 0.001. There is no significant difference in mobile dependence scores between the two age groups. Individuals younger than 20 years old have a mean score of 10.95 ($SD = 2.94$), while those older than 20 years old have a mean score of 10.74 ($SD = 3.31$), with a t -value of 0.63 and a p -value of 0.525. For various aspects of quality of life, including overall quality of life and general health, physical health, psychological health, social relations, and environment, there are no significant differences between the two age groups. The mean scores for overall quality of life and general health are 7.28 ($SD = 1.24$) for those younger than 20 years old and 7.26 ($SD = 1.38$) for those older than 20 years old, with a t -value of 0.19 and a p -value of 0.846. Similarly, physical health

scores are nearly identical ($M = 57.45$, $SD = 12.50$ for <20 years old; $M = 57.25$, $SD = 12.60$ for >20 years old), with a t -value of 0.14 and a p -value of 0.889. Psychological health scores, social relations scores, and environment scores also show no significant differences, with p -values of 0.657, 0.728, and 0.745, respectively.

Table 5.7 Comparison between Age category on the General weighted average, mobile dependence, and Quality of life

	<20 years old		>20 years old		<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>		
General weighted average	88.51	3.85	86.18	5.06	4.88	<0.001
Mobile dependence score	10.95	2.94	10.74	3.31	0.63	0.525
Quality of life						
Overall quality of life and general health	7.28	1.24	7.26	1.38	0.19	0.846
Physical health	57.45	12.50	57.25	12.60	0.14	0.889
Psychological	60.80	14.20	61.51	15.30	-0.44	0.657
Social relations	66.32	19.20	65.58	19.10	0.35	0.728
Environment	65.83	12.90	65.36	13.70	0.33	0.745

Table 6.1. presents the pairwise correlation result on general weight average, mobile dependence, and quality of life. Correlation coefficients and significance levels are provided to illustrate the relationships between these variables. Physical health shows a significant negative correlation with mobile dependence score ($r = -0.19$, $p < .01$), implying that higher mobile dependence is associated with poorer physical health. Additionally, physical health is positively correlated with overall quality of life and general health ($r = 0.46$, $p < .01$), indicating that better physical health contributes to a higher overall quality of life and general health. Psychological health is negatively correlated with mobile dependence score ($r = -0.21$, $p < .01$), suggesting that greater mobile dependence is linked to poorer psychological health. Psychological health also shows strong positive correlations with overall quality of life and general health ($r = 0.58$, $p < .01$) and physical health ($r = 0.61$, $p < .01$), indicating that better psychological health is associated with higher overall quality of life and better physical health. Social relations are positively correlated with the general weighted average ($r = 0.16$, $p < .05$), suggesting that better social relations are associated with higher academic performance. Social relations are also negatively correlated with mobile dependence score ($r = -0.11$, $p < .05$), indicating that higher mobile dependence is associated with poorer social relations. Furthermore, social relations show significant positive correlations with overall quality of life and general health ($r = 0.38$, $p < .01$), physical health ($r = 0.38$, $p < .01$), and psychological health ($r = 0.47$, $p < .01$), suggesting that better social relations contribute to higher quality of life, better physical health, and better psychological health. The environment is positively correlated with the general weighted average ($r = 0.12$, $p < .05$), indicating that a better environment is associated with higher academic performance. It also shows a significant negative correlation with mobile dependence score ($r = -0.22$, $p < .01$), suggesting that

higher mobile dependence is linked to a poorer environment. Moreover, the environment is strongly positively correlated with overall quality of life and general health ($r = 0.50, p < .01$), physical health ($r = 0.55, p < .01$), psychological health ($r = 0.62, p < .01$), and social relations ($r = 0.50, p < .01$), indicating that a better environment contributes to higher overall quality of life, better physical health, improved psychological health, and better social relations.

Table 6.1. Pairwise correlation results on general weighted average, mobile dependence, and Quality of life

	n	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6
1. General weighted average	34	87.5		-					
	9	9	4.51	0.24**					
2. Mobile dependence score	34	10.8			-				
	9	7	3.09	-0.01	0.003				
3. Overall quality of life and general health	34					-			
	9	7.27	1.29	-0.01	0.05	-0.09			
4. Physical health	34	57.3	12.5				0.46*		
	9	7	3	-0.07	0.04	0.19**	*		
5. Psychological	34	61.0	14.6					0.58*	0.61*
	9	8	3	0.03	0.002	0.21**	*	*	
6. Social relations	34	66.0	19.1						0.47*
	9	3	4	-0.06	0.16*	-0.11*	0.38*	0.38*	*
7. Environment	34	65.6	13.2						
	9	4	0	0.01	0.12*	0.22**	0.50*	0.55*	0.62*
							*	*	*

* $p < .05$. ** $p < .01$.

Table 6.2 presents the structural equation modeling (SEM) results and reveals significant relationships between latent variables. Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSE) = 0.062, p -value = 0.212. Based on the rule of thumbs, an RMSE value ranging from 0.05-0.08 will be deemed reasonably fit. In addition, the p -value was not significant, which means that the hypothesis of close fit was supported. Further, a CFI value greater than 0.95, and an SRMR less than 0.08 are threshold values of model adequacy. The model gave a Comparative Fit Index (CFI) = 0.971; Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) = 0.036. Based on this set of fit measures, the researchers concluded that the model as specified was plausible and adequate.

The output from the structural equation modeling (SEM) analysis provides standardized coefficients (factor loadings) for items on latent variables (LV), along with confidence intervals (CI), standard errors (SE), Z values (Wald test), and p -values. The factor loadings range from .626 to .897, indicating that the relationships between items and factors are substantial (note that there are no strict cutoffs for acceptable loadings). Notably, all coefficients are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

Moreover, the researchers examined the relationships between Mobile phone dependence, General weighted average, and Quality of life. The results revealed associations between these variables. Firstly, it was found that mobile phone dependence showed a negligible positive relationship with the general weighted average, suggesting that excessive reliance on mobile phones may not significantly impact academic performance (coefficient = 0.02, $p = 0.758$). However, a more concerning finding emerged regarding the link between mobile phone dependence and quality of life. Here, a moderate negative relationship was observed, indicating that higher levels of mobile

phone dependence were associated with lower quality of life scores (coefficient = -0.25, $p < 0.001$). Conversely, the relationship between academic performance and quality of life appeared less pronounced. While a weak positive relationship was noted, it failed to reach statistical significance (coefficient = 0.08, $p = 0.155$).

Table 6.2. Structural equation modeling

<i>Latent variables</i>	<i>Item</i>	<i>Estimate</i>	<i>SE</i>	<i>95% CI</i>		<i>p</i>
				<i>LL</i>	<i>UL</i>	
Quality of life	Overall quality of life and general health	0.67	0.043	0.59	0.76	<0.001
	Physical health	0.72	0.033	0.65	0.78	<0.001
	Psychological	0.84	0.025	0.79	0.89	<0.001
	Social relations	0.59	0.042	0.51	0.67	<0.001
	Environment	0.78	0.031	0.72	0.84	<0.001
Mobile phone dependence	General weighted average	0.02	0.052	-	0.12	0.758
	Quality of life	-0.25	0.058	-	-	<0.001
General weighted average	Quality of life	0.08	0.055	-	0.19	0.155

RMSE=0.062, p-value=0.212

CFI=0.971, srmr=0.036

DISCUSSION

In today's era where mobile phone use has become inevitable, the increasing susceptibility to mobile phone dependence and its effects on different areas of life has been a concern and a topic of extensive research globally. More specifically, one area of concern is the susceptibility to mobile phone dependence among students and its possible effects on academic performance and quality of life. Since the use of technology nowadays has become unavoidable, as it has been integrated into everyday activities, sufficient knowledge is needed to identify possible ways to maximize its benefits while minimizing its potential consequences on different aspects, including academic performance and quality of life. This study is among the few local studies that assess the relationship and effect of mobile phone dependence on academic performance and quality of life among tertiary-level students.

Extent of mobile dependence

Results of the smartphone compulsion test highlights that a large majority of the respondents spend more time on their mobile phones than they realize (306, 87.68%), often lose track of time when using their phones (264, 75.64%), and regularly pass time mindlessly while using their devices (310, 88.83%). This suggests that many of the

respondents may have a notable unawareness of the actual amount of time they spend on their devices, which is a common trait observed in many mobile phone users (Lancaster University, 2015).

Meanwhile, a large percentage of the respondents also acknowledged an increase in their smartphone usage (250, 71.63%) and reported that they wish to be less involved with their phones (275, 78.80%). While this seems to contradict the previous finding, it may imply that even if individuals recognize their excessive mobile phone use and desire to be less engaged, there is often a conflict between their awareness and their behavior. This conflict may be due to factors such as the benefits that mobile phone use contributes to activities and purposes (Basu et al., 2018).

Moreover, there is a noticeable preference of virtual communication on over half of the respondents. On average, 60.17% of the respondents reported that they prefer texting, tweeting, or emailing over in-person conversations. This suggests a change in communication norms and an inclination towards more modern modes of communication. This finding may be due to different factors, such as cost-effectiveness, convenience, easy accessibility, flexibility, and enhanced connectivity that virtual communication may bring (Naha, 2024). Some may also highlight the use of mobile phones in communicating decreases the anxiety of an individual compared with face-to-face interaction (Sahimi et al., 2022). However, it is equally important to highlight the negative effects that this mode of communication may cause, such as impairment of in person interaction and the ability to have deeper and spontaneous conversations (Turkle 2015, as cited in Suttie, 2015).

Findings also reflect the impact that smartphone use has on the respondents' daily routines. 58.45% (204) of the respondents reported sleeping with their phone nearby and 72.21% (252) reported that using their phone is a regular part of their meal settings. It is important to highlight the potential adverse effects of these behaviors. Existing literature suggests how proximity to smartphones may negatively affect the quality of sleep, due to different factors, such as blue light emission that suppresses melatonin (a hormone that regulates sleep) production (Oh et al., 2015), or increased sleep interruptions due to notifications and urge to check messages (Hillcrest Hospital South, 2024). In addition, using mobile phones during meals may also negatively affect eating habits, such as decreased food intake (University of Illinois, 2020), or increased caloric intake (La Marra et al., 2020). Studies also emphasize its detrimental impact on face-to-face social interactions during meals, leading to less enjoyable and less meaningful engagements (University of British Columbia, 2018).

In addition, more than half of the respondents (223, 63.90%) reported using their mobile phones even when it interrupts other activities. This may be in line with the consequent finding that a large number of respondents also reported decreased productivity due to mobile phone use (278, 79.66%). This aligns with previous literature suggesting that smartphones can lead to distractions, pulling one away from intended tasks to be done, leading to procrastination and decreased productivity (Koessmeier & Büttner, 2021; Robinson, 2024).

However, an alarming result is that also at least half of the respondents, (189, 54.15%) reported using their mobile phones during activities that require attention, such as driving. This is a concern, as stated in the recent study of Kim et al. (2017) that mobile phone dependent individuals may have an increased tendency of compromising safety by using mobile phones while engaging in concentration-demanding activities.

The emotional and psychological impact of smartphone dependency was also evident, with a high percentage of respondents reporting they feel reluctant to be without their phones even for a short time (238, 68.19%), and feel uneasy when they accidentally leave their devices (275, 78.80%). This is further emphasized by also a large number of respondents claiming they feel an intense urge to check notifications (255, 73.07%) and mindlessly check their phones multiple times a day even when there is likely nothing new or important to see (264, 75.64%). These behaviors align with the phenomenon of “nomophobia” or no mobile phone phobia observed by recent studies, which refers to the fear of being without or unable to use one’s phone (Notara et al. 2021).

The average overall mobile dependence score among the respondents was 10.87 (SD=3.088). Alarmingly, according to the criteria set by Dr. David Greenfield on the Smartphone Compulsion Test, this score is indicative of high mobile phone dependence, in a level in which they are suggested for a consultation with a healthcare professional. This suggests that a significant portion of the respondents have a level of mobile phone dependence that may potentially compromise their overall health and functioning. This strongly suggests a need for targeted interventions to address mobile phone dependence and its possible negative effects on different aspects.

Level of Quality of Life

Overall quality of life and general health

Overall quality of life and general health were rated on average 7.27 by the respondents, out of a highest score of 10. The relatively high average score may indicate that most of the respondents have a positive view of their well-being. Highest percentage of respondents expressed they are “satisfied” with their quality of life (190, 54.44%) and general health (159, 45.56%). A very small portion of respondents on the other hand rated their quality of life as “very poor” (3, 0.86%), and their health also as “very poor” (5, 1.43%). Many factors may have contributed to these positive perceptions, including the condition of physical, social, psychological, and environmental aspects such as access to quality healthcare, loving relationships, meaningful work or volunteer opportunities, leisure activities, adequate rest, a healthy diet, and regular exercise (Kagan, 2024).

Physical health domain

The average score reported in the physical health domain is 22.99 out of a highest score of 35, and an average transformed scale score of 57.37. Notably, in terms of physical pain, the largest portion (163, 46.70%) reported moderate amounts of pain, while some (48, 13.75%) reported they are very much affected. A majority also expressed their need

for medical treatment to function in moderate amounts (135, 38.68%). Regarding energy levels, the majority reported moderate energy levels (165, 47.28%), with only a small portion reporting they have completely sufficient energy (25, 7.16%). Meanwhile, 11.75% (41) reported they have little energy and 1.72% (6) even claim they do not at all have enough energy for everyday life. In terms of mobility, while the largest portion (157, 44.99%) expressed satisfaction, a significant portion (146, 41.83%) expressed they view their mobility as neither poor nor good. In terms of sleep, the highest majority (145, 41.55%) reported they are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied with their sleep. Similarly, the largest portion of respondents also claimed they are neither satisfied nor dissatisfied in terms of ability to perform daily living activities (153, 43.84%) and their capacity for work (173, 49.57%).

These findings suggest that while the respondents' physical health may be relatively satisfactory, they may also be experiencing some limitations or challenges in their physical health, including mobility, energy levels, and pain.

The majority reports of pain being moderate may indicate it is significant enough to be noticeable and distracting, which may affect normal functioning or everyday activities (Specialists Hospital Shreveport, n.d.). Similarly, it is also important to note that only a very small number of respondents reported that they have sufficient energy for everyday activities, and a number of respondents even reported they had no energy at all. This may also affect their everyday activities as low levels of energy may cause impairment in focus and concentration, as well as in sustaining physical effort in order to complete basic tasks (Galan, 2018). There may be underlying issues affecting the respondents' energy levels, including nutrition, physical exercise, mental health, and the quality of sleep. Programs that support regular exercise, a balanced diet, and mental health assistance may be recommended as it can help lower fatigue and increase overall energy levels (Harvard Health, 2023).

The presence of pain and low energy levels may contribute to the majority viewing their mobility, ability to perform activities and capacity for work as neutral, neither satisfied or dissatisfied, which suggests they recognize these could be higher or better. This is an area of concern since this may possibly affect productivity and well-being.

In addition, the quality of sleep being mostly reported as neither satisfactory or dissatisfactory also suggests that the respondents see a possibility of their sleep to be of better quality. A good quality of sleep is essential because it contributes to physical health, cognitive function, and emotional well-being (National Institutes of Health, 2022). Sleep length and quality can be increased using interventions such as cognitive-behavioral treatment for insomnia, sleep hygiene education, and relaxation methods (Van Straten et al., 2018).

Psychological domain

The average score obtained in the psychological domain was 20.60 out of a highest score of 30 and an average psychological transformed scale score of 61.08. Largest majority

reported that they “very much” enjoyed life (165, 47.28%) and found life to be meaningful (147, 42.12%). This indicates that in general, the respondents have a positive view of their lives, which is important as purpose and life satisfaction play in fostering psychological well-being (Steger et al., 2019).

However, in terms of being able to concentrate, the largest portion of the respondents (189, 54.15%) reported only being able to concentrate “moderately”. This may indicate that the respondents may have the ability to focus, but only for a limited time, or that they can only do so with much effort.

Similarly, the highest majority also reported only to be moderately satisfied with their bodily appearance (142, 40.69%), and were neither satisfied nor dissatisfied with themselves (133, 38.11%). This may indicate that the respondents may have mixed feelings or may be ambivalent regarding the way they view their appearance and themselves in general. This ambivalence may be contributed by many factors, such as societal standards, personal experiences, and mental well-being (Mfa, 2020).

Notably, the largest portions of the respondents reported having negative feelings quite often (132, 37.82%) and very often (99, 28.37%). This suggests a prevalence of negative feelings among the respondents that require possible interventions.

Social relationships domain

Average social relationships score among the respondents is 10.92 out of a highest score of 15, with the transformed scale score averaging 66.03. Majority expressed their satisfaction in personal relationships (149, 42.69%), while a significant number expressed neutrality (106, 30.37%). Meanwhile, the majority also expressed neutrality in their satisfaction regarding sex life (128, 36.68%) while most reported satisfaction with the support they get from friends (132, 37.82%). Results suggest that respondents have a moderately positive view of their social relationships in general, but have varying levels of satisfaction with different aspects of their relationships. Reports of “neutral” suggest they may see a need or a possibility of improvement, in order to produce stronger social connections and satisfaction.

Environmental domain

The environmental domain had an average score of 28.48 out of a highest score of 40, and an average transformed scale score of 65.64. Majority expressed feeling “very much” safe (150, 42.98%), having a moderately healthy physical environment (146, 41.83%), and were satisfied with the conditions of their living place (147, 42.12%).

This indicates that the majority of the respondents have a positive perception of their safety and living environment.

Most respondents also expressed moderate amounts of financial adequacy (134, 38.40%) and opportunity for leisure (158, 45.27%). This may indicate that while they view

these aspects as satisfactory, there may be a possibility for further improvement in order to enhance quality of life.

Information was noted to be mostly available by the majority (152, 43.55%). Most expressed satisfaction with their access to health services (149, 42.69%), while the majority expressed dissatisfaction with their mode of transportation (153, 43.84%). The availability of information and satisfaction with access to health services are generally positive, indicating that respondents feel adequately informed and have satisfactory access to essential services. However, a negative finding was observed in terms of their satisfaction with modes of transportation, with most of the respondents expressing their dissatisfaction. This suggests that improvements may be needed in this aspect to enhance accessibility and convenience for respondents.

Comparison between sex on the General weighted average, mobile dependence, and Quality of life

General Weighted Average

In terms of General Weighted Average, results showed that females tend to have a slightly higher average compared to males, although this difference is not statistically significant. However, some previous studies have also shown females having higher academic performance than males. (Wrigley-Asante, 2023; Parajuli, 2017). Results of a related study offers a promising explanation, highlighting a difference in personality between the sexes, particularly higher levels of conscientiousness among female students. The study suggests that females tend to be more responsible, hardworking and organized, which contributes to their better academic outcomes (Verbree, 2022).

Mobile Dependence

Females also scored higher than males in mobile phone dependence, but still without statistical significance. These results support other studies, that female students tend to have higher prevalence of smartphone dependence. (Alhafi et al., 2024)

Quality of Life

Overall quality of life and general health scores were nearly identical between males and females, and no statistical difference was found. However, males had higher scores in the physical, psychological, and environmental domains, which showed statistical difference.

This aligns with previous literature suggesting that males tend to have more positive perceptions of their health and well-being compared to females (European Institute for Gender Equality, 2024). A possible explanation is offered by several studies explaining that women tend to be more sensitive to stress than men, which may make them more vulnerable to challenges in their well-being such as depression and trauma (Dowthwaite-Walsh, 2018).

Comparison among Colleges on the General weighted average, mobile dependence, and Quality of life

General Weighted Average

Results showed significant differences in GWA among the colleges, with College of Information Technology having the highest average of 90.70, and College of Engineering and Architecture having the lowest of 84.20. Many factors may have contributed to this, such as types of classes students take, the classroom conditions, variations in teaching, and differences in students' academic effort or skills which may have impacted students' general weighted averages (Allensworth et al., 2019).

Mobile Dependence

Interestingly, no significant difference was observed in terms of mobile phone dependence across all departments. Highest mean mobile phone dependence scores were noted in College of SBPA (12.20) and lowest in College of Education (9.38). This suggests that students' reliance on mobile phones is consistent regardless of the department they belong to, which further highlights the widespread use of mobile phones among all students.

Quality of Life

Similarly, no significant differences were found on overall quality of life and general health across all college departments. However, a significant difference was noted in the social relations component, with the College of Information and Technology having the highest mean score (73.40) and College of Engineering and Architecture having the lowest (57.60). In the environmental domain, there was also a significant difference among colleges, with College of Education (70.80) having the highest mean and School of Arts and Sciences (60.10) having the lowest.

This indicates that while overall quality of life and general health did not vary across all departments, differences were observed in terms of social relations and environmental factors which may also potentially impact students' well-being.

Specifically, it is interesting to note that the department with the highest social relations score (College of Information and Technology) also had the highest GWA, and the department with the lowest social relations score (College of Engineering and Architecture) corresponded to the lowest GWA. This finding aligns with literature suggesting that good social interactions can improve learning and positively affect academic performance in different ways, such as increased learning from sharing ideas and experiences with peers, boosting self-confidence, and promoting a positive attitude towards learning (Li et al., 2018, as cited in Ali et al., 2022; Popirtac, 2022)

Comparison among year-level categories on the General weighted average, mobile dependence, and Quality of life

General Weighted Average

Results revealed significant differences among students' General Weighted Average (GWA) among the year levels. Specifically, first year level students had the highest mean GWA (88.90), and fourth year students had the lowest (85.30). This may be due to different factors, such as a heavier workload that is expected as year level increases, which may cause stress, burnout, decreased motivation which negatively impacts learning outcomes (Kanwal et al., 2023). Moreover, some literature suggest that students who are reaching the end of their courses may experience an intense lack of motivation which may be due to different factors such as detachment anxiety, anticipation of starting a new chapter in their lives, or mainly due to feelings of burnout, which may lead to procrastination and loss of interest in studies, leading to decreased academic outcomes (Wallis, 2024).

Mobile Dependence

No significant difference was observed between mobile phone dependence scores across year levels. These results support the study of Baek and Cho (2017), which found that addiction to smartphones among college students, may not be influenced by their year level and could have a significant impact on their quality of life.

Quality of Life

The overall quality of life and general health scores also showed no significant difference. Third year students had the highest mean score of 7.44 and fourth-year students had the lowest of 7.03. Similarly, no significant differences were also observed in all specific domains. This may indicate that year level may not be a decisive factor in terms of their quality of life.

Comparison between Use of mobile on Internet search/web browsing on the General weighted average, mobile dependence, and Quality of life

There were no significant differences in the general weighted average, mobile dependence, or quality of life between students who used their mobile phones for internet searching or web browsing and those who did not. This suggests that casual online browsing may not strongly impact mobile dependence, academic performance or well-being.

Comparison between Use of mobile on Entertainment on the General weighted average, mobile dependence, and Quality of life

Similarly, using mobile phones for entertainment purposes did not significantly affect general weighted average, mobile dependence, or quality of life scores. This indicates

that entertainment use alone may not have a measurable influence on mobile dependence, academic or personal well-being.

Comparison between Use of mobile on Communication on the General weighted average, mobile dependence, and Quality of life

The results showed no significant differences between users and non-users regarding general weighted average, mobile dependence, or quality of life for mobile phone use in communication. This implies that mobile communication habits may not directly impact mobile dependence, academic outcomes or perceived quality of life.

Comparison between Use of mobile on Academic/learning purpose on the General weighted average, mobile dependence, and Quality of life

A significant difference was found in the general weighted average between users and non-users of mobile phones for academic purposes, with users showing lower academic performance. This suggests that using phones for academic tasks may hinder learning rather than enhance it for some learners, potentially reducing their academic performance. (Mahsud et al., 2020).

Comparison between Use of mobile on Buying products/Online shopping purpose on the General weighted average, mobile dependence, and Quality of life

Mobile phone use for buying products or online shopping showed no significant differences in general weighted average, mobile dependence, or quality of life. This suggests that shopping activities via mobile devices do not significantly affect mobile dependence, academic or personal outcomes.

Comparison between Use of mobile on Gaming purpose on the General weighted average, mobile dependence, and Quality of life

Mobile phone use for gaming purposes did not yield significant differences in general weighted average, mobile dependence, or quality of life. This indicates that gaming, in this context, may not have a strong measurable impact on these variables.

Comparison among the number of devices owned among respondent categories on the General weighted average, mobile dependence, and Quality of life

No significant differences were observed in General weighted average, mobile dependence and quality of life according to number of devices. These findings suggest that the number of devices alone does not have an impact on these three components. This can likely support the claim of Mohd Mothar et al. (2013, as cited in Surat et al., 2021) that it is not the number of gadgets but the selection of a gadget that can be an approach to identifying the advantages and disadvantages of gadget consumption, the impact on quality of life, and how users control their usage.

Comparison among the duration of device use categories on the General weighted average, mobile dependence, and Quality of life

General Weighted Average

The results of the study showed a minimal increase in General Weighted Average as duration of device use increased. The mean GWA was highest for respondents who reported to use their mobile phones for more than 20 hours (91.90). However, this increase was not statistically significant. This suggests a possible positive effect of increased mobile phone use to academic performance, although very minimal. This opposes the common idea that increased mobile phone use was associated with lower GPA (Ng, et al., 2017). Additionally, this highlights that the effects of smartphone use on academic performance is not solely determined by the total time spent on smartphones, but rather by how effectively they manage their smartphone usage (Troll et al., 2021).

Mobile Dependence

A statistically significant difference was observed on the mobile phone dependence scores of different durations of mobile phone use. This indicates that the amount of time spent using mobile phones has a measurable impact on mobile phone dependence. However, interestingly, the results do not show a consistent increase in mobile phone dependence as duration of use increased. The average dependence score for respondents who reported 1-2 hours of mobile phone use is 10.4, which decreased to 10.0 in those who reported 3-6 hours category. Meanwhile, the average dependency scores increased in those who used their mobile phones for 7-10 hours (11.2), 11-15 hours (11.4), 16-20 hours (11.4). This trend may imply that mobile dependence tends to increase as hours of mobile phone use exceeds 6 hours, which aligns with some previous research studies that had similar findings (Martínez-Sánchez et al., 2020). Notably however, the average dependency scores decreased to 10.5 for those who reported more than 20 hours of mobile phone use. This may then also indicate that other factors, aside from the extent of mobile phone use alone, may contribute to dependence. (Meena et al., 2021). Further investigation may be helpful to understand possible underlying causes of this observed trend.

Quality of Life

A statistically significant difference was also observed in terms of Quality of Life and general health according to different durations of mobile phone use. This implies that the duration of mobile phone use has a significant impact on quality of life.

However, varied results showed in different components of quality of life. In terms of physical health and social relations, no significant difference showed across different durations of mobile use. This implies that duration of mobile phone use does not have a significant impact on these components.

It is possible that other factors, such as the nature of physical activities and face-to-face social interactions, play a more crucial role in determining physical health and social relationships than the duration of mobile phone use.

However, significant differences showed in psychological and environmental scores. Specifically, highest scores were also noted in those who reported 3-6 hours of mobile use, and lowest in those who reported more than 20 hours. This indicates that moderate mobile phone use is beneficial for psychological well-being and satisfaction with one's environment.

It is important to note that findings showed 3-6 hours of mobile phone use associated with the highest overall QoL and general health scores, as well as the best psychological and environmental QoL scores. This suggests that moderate mobile phone use can provide significant benefits. (Sela et al., 2022)

Comparison between Age category on the General weighted average, mobile dependence, and Quality of life

General weighted average

Results showed that respondents above 20 years old had a significantly higher General Weighted Average compared to those 20 years old and below. This finding aligns with the notion that older students, typically in their 20s, are considered to be wiser, more mature, and with more life experience. These may contribute to them having a stronger motivation for studying and may use deeper and strategic approaches which positively affects their productivity and benefits their academic outcomes. (Tadese et al., 2022)

Mobile Phone Dependence

There is no observed significant difference in mobile dependence scores between the two age groups. This finding implies that age may not be a decisive factor in terms of mobile phone dependence, which suggests that individuals of all ages could be equally susceptible to it.

Quality of Life

Aspects of quality of life, including overall quality of life and general health, physical health, psychological health, social relations, and environment showed no statistical difference between the two age groups. This finding suggests that age may not be a determining factor in terms of these aspects of well-being.

Pairwise correlation on general weighted average, mobile dependence, and Quality of life

This part of the discussion highlights the pairwise correlations between the variables included in this study, showing the independent relationships among them. This is to

emphasize how each pair of variables is related in order to provide insights into their individual interactions excluding the influence of other variables.

Physical Health and Mobile Dependence

Results showed a significant negative correlation between physical health and mobile dependence. This finding aligns with several previous literature suggesting that mobile phone dependence has a detrimental impact on physical health, associating it with physical inactivity, inadequate sleep, overweight or obesity, and reports of physical pain and discomfort (Alotaibi et al., 2022; Ratan et al. in 2022).

Psychological Health and Mobile Dependence

The results also revealed a significant negative correlation between psychological health and mobile dependence. This again aligns with existing studies suggesting that problematic mobile phone use not only impacts physical health, but even psychological well-being. (Daniyal et al. in 2022) High levels of mobile phone dependence has been previously associated with increased tendency for psychological disturbances, including stress, anxiety, depression, and loneliness (Winkler et al., 2020; Robinson, 2024).

Social Relations and Mobile Dependence

Social relations are also negatively correlated with mobile dependence score, reflecting the consequences it has on interpersonal relationships. This finding aligns with existing literature, indicating that mobile dependence was associated with greater difficulties in maintaining healthy interpersonal relationships (Iram, 2023). This may be due to different factors, such as time displacement, as excessive time spent on gadgets decreases time for interacting with others in person (Dwyer et al., 2017), preference for online interactions over face-to-face interactions which may lead to feelings of isolation (Jameslopresti, 2023), or distraction and inattention during conversations which may lead to misunderstandings or lack of connection (Hippe, 2023).

Environmental Health and Mobile Dependence

A significant negative correlation was also found between mobile dependence score and environmental health, indicating that mobile phone dependence may arise from a poor environment. This may be due to several factors, such as escapism, wherein people use their smartphones to get away from their actual environment which may be uncomfortable or unfavorable for them (Calif, 2018). Some literature also suggests that lack of green spaces or safe outdoor areas for alternative recreational activities can also contribute to increased mobile phone use which may negatively affect mental health and well-being (Oswald, 2020).

Physical, Psychological Social, and Environmental Health on Overall Quality of Life and General Health

Results of this study showed that physical, psychological, social, and environmental domains were all positively correlated with overall quality of life and general health. This highlights the importance of a holistic approach to health, that all aspects are important to be considered in order to attain an optimum quality of life and general health. (St. Catherine University, 2022).

Notably, psychological health also showed strong positive correlation with physical health, supporting the idea of a deep interconnection between these two components. Existing literature has claimed that individuals experiencing psychological disturbance, such as chronic stress, anxiety, or depression are more likely to develop physical health problems. This also makes them more susceptible to engage in unhealthy behaviors such as smoking, unhealthy diet, and lack of exercise. Consequently, those experiencing physical health problems may also be more prone to experiencing psychological distress (WebMD, 2023).

Social relations also were positively correlated with physical health and psychological health, supporting existing literature that claims that individuals with wider and healthier social relationships tend to have reduced stress and heart-related risks, thus having better physical and mental health (National Institutes of Health, 2017).

Meanwhile, environmental health is also strongly positively correlated with physical health, psychological health, and social relations. This highlights the interconnectedness of the environment and overall health. A healthy environment has been proven to reduce physical health risks, lead to reduced stress, depression and anxiety, and provide opportunities for social interactions and strengthening of social bonds (Herman, 2024; College of Natural Resources, 2022).

Social Relations and Academic performance

Social relations are positively correlated with general weighted average, further supporting the previously stated finding that better social relations may contribute to improved learning, resulting in higher academic performance.

Environmental Health and Academic Performance

The environment was also found to be positively correlated with the general weighted average. This is in line with existing literature suggesting that the environment has a crucial role in an individual's academic performance, suggesting that students with a positive learning environment are more likely to be motivated and have significantly increased learning ability. On the other contrary, students exposed to environments that may be uncomfortable, noisy, or full of distractions may find it more challenging to stay engaged and retain information (Hendrix, 2019).

Overall relationship and effect of mobile dependence, academic performance, and quality of life

This part of the discussion highlights the overall relationships and effects of the three variables that were analyzed using Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). This approach reveals the intertwined relationships and influences among these variables, which gives a deeper insight and understanding of their interactions.

Mobile phone dependence and Academic performance

The results of this study showed that mobile phone dependence showed a minimal positive relationship with the general weighted average. This implies that mobile phone dependence may not significantly impact academic performance. This opposes the common idea presented in many literature that mobile phone dependence has a significant negative impact on academic performance (Samaha & Hawi, 2016; Santhi & Rajesh, 2020; Felisoni & Godoi, 2018). This highlights the complexity of the relationship between mobile dependence and academic performance, especially in the present time where gadgets are widely used for academic purposes. A much recent study even showed that students who had higher mobile phone use had better academic performances compared to students who had low smartphone use (Wang et al., 2022). This may indicate a need for further research to better understand the relationship between these two variables.

On another note, this may also highlight the idea that the nature of mobile phone use is an important determinant of its effect on academic performance. While some suggest it usually becomes a distraction and results in decreased productivity, several studies have also shown that students who utilize mobile phones for educational purposes have higher academic performance, related to increased access to extensive information, communication with peers and lecturers, aiding in research and assignments, and enhancing educational opportunities (Zhao et al., 2018, Lin et al., 2021, Chukwuere, 2018). On the other hand, this could also imply that other factors, such as study habits, might play a more critical role in influencing academic performance (Global Indian International School, 2023).

Mobile Phone Dependence and Quality of Life

Contrary to the academic performance, mobile dependence showed a moderate negative relationship with quality of life. Specifically, lowest quality of life scores were noted for those who reported more than 20 hours of mobile phone use. This aligns with several existing literature suggesting that higher mobile phone dependence has a notable negative impact on quality of life (Volkmer & Lerner, 2019; Alotaibi et al., 2022, Daniyal et al., 2022, Winkler et al., 2020). This finding is consistent and maybe explained with the negative associations revealed in the pairwise correlations results of this study previously shown, where mobile phone dependence is noted to have a negative impact on all domains of physical, psychological, social, and environmental health and well-being. The findings highlight the potential adverse effects of excessive mobile phone use on students'

well-being, emphasizing the need for balanced and mindful usage to maintain a higher quality of life. (Sela et al., 2022)

Academic Performance and Quality of Life

However, no significant relationship was found on academic performance and quality of life. This indicates that better academic performance is not clearly linked to an improved quality of life, contradicting many existing literature claiming that higher academic performance is associated with better quality of life (Shareef et al., 2015; Chattu et al., 2020; Adelantado-Renau et al., 2022). This may imply that academic success alone may not be sufficient to enhance students' overall well-being and that other factors, such as physical state, psychological state and social relationships, play a crucial role in determining their quality of life (Szegegi et al., 2024).

Conclusions

This research investigates the mobile phone dependence, academic performance and quality of life of college students. Furthermore, it also aims to identify any correlations between these factors and the demographic characteristics of the respondents. The mean age of the respondents is 20.23 years, with a predominant male presence comprising 57.13%, slightly surpassing the female, which constitutes 42.69% of the total respondents. The most prevalent college courses among the respondents are Bachelor of Science in Nursing representing 15.76%, and Bachelor of Science in Architecture, accounting for 11.75% collectively. Additionally, the majority of respondents belong to the first-year level.

Students own at least one mobile phone with a significant portion allocation 7-10 hours daily for primarily web browsing activities. The collective academic performance, as reflected by a general weighted average of 87.59, signifies a good average grade among the respondents indicating proficient academic performance. It has been concluded, based on the research findings, that the 99.43% of the total respondents score above the normal, with a notable 85.10% exhibiting significant dependence on mobile phones posing a noteworthy concern. The mean overall mobile dependence score among respondents is 10.87, surpassing the normal range of 1-2. Consequently, according to the criteria established by Dr. David Greenfield, Center for Internet and Technology Addiction, it suggests that the respondents may benefit from seeking psychological intervention.

Additionally, the study's findings indicate that respondents' assessment of their quality of life suggests that they are satisfied in their overall quality of life and general health. Furthermore, the evaluation of respondent's assessment posted neutrality on the quality of life in terms of physical domain. Notably, a majority of respondents reported experiencing frequent negative affect within the psychological domain. Moreover, respondents expressed contentment with their quality of life concerning social relationships and the environment. Notable distinction emerges in the overall weighted mean scores between respondents aged above 20 years and those aged 20 years and

below. Conversely, no statistically significant is evident in academic performance, as measured by the general weighted average and mobile dependence scores, between male and female respondents, suggesting equitable academic achievement and mobile phones reliance across genders.

Similarly, no significant difference was observed between male and female assessments on quality of life and general health as well as in the social relation domain. However, statistically significant discrepancies are evident in physical health, psychological well-being, and environmental assessments, with males exhibiting higher scores, indicative of greater engagement in physical activities, improved psychological states, and better environmental conditions compared to females.

A significant difference on the general weighted mean of the respondents coming from different levels was revealed, potentially attributed to variations in subject difficulty across academic year levels. Nevertheless, mobile dependency and the overall quality of life and general health remains the same across all the year levels. This means that quality of life is not associated with the year level of the students.

The duration of device usage manifests a statistically significant difference concerning mobile dependency, overall quality of life, general health, and the psychological and environmental domains. This indicates that the duration of mobile devices utilization exerts a significant influence on both the comprehensive quality of life and psychological and environmental aspects experienced by the respondents.

In addition, the number of devices does not yield a statistically significant variance in the aforementioned variables. This suggests that an increased number of devices does not correlate with higher or lower academic performance, a higher dependency or a better quality of life.

It was concluded that there is a negative correlation revealed between mobile dependence and quality of life which is concerning knowing that a negative correlation implies that a higher mobile dependency equates to a poorer quality of life. Additionally, the study's outcomes demonstrated positive correlations across the physical, psychological, social and environmental domains with both overall quality of life and general health. Notably, psychological health also showed strong positive correlation with physical health.

The findings suggest that dependence on mobile phones does not exert a significant impact on academic performance, which means it does not improve or impair the academic performance of a student. Additionally, a weak positive correlation between general weighted mean and quality of life is not considered statistically significant. Thus, General weighted mean is not associated with the quality of life.

Recommendations

The findings of this study support the assertion that the data indicate elevated levels of mobile dependence among the respondents, surpassing standard dependency thresholds. Consequently, the implementation of awareness programs aimed at addressing the adverse outcome of mobile dependency is recommended. Furthermore, it is advised that counseling and support services be made accessible to students exhibiting mobile phone reliance. These services should offer personalized strategies aimed at managing and mitigating dependency, thereby enhancing overall well-being. It was also suggested that schools and other stakeholders consider giving seminars or awareness orientation with regards to the proper use of mobile phones, its effect and its benefits. Educational institutions should consider developing policies that encourage limited and purposeful use of mobile phones on campus.

Physical and psychological quality of life were observed to have the least scores. This opens the idea of having or considering physical and psychological development programs that involve physical activities and improves the mental condition of the students. This may be considered not only by the school but also the community since physical activity and psychological development can be improved outside the school premise.

It is recommended to assess the distribution of workload across various academic years, as a lower general weighted average was observed among higher year levels. The researchers propose a moderate mobile phone usage duration of 3-6 hours, given that study findings indicate that individuals within this range tend to exhibit higher quality of life and enhanced academic performance. Moreover, students should be aware of the repercussions of the excessive use of mobile phones so they can limit themselves or at least use the said device efficiently.

Additionally, it was also recommended to different government agencies and community leaders to consider the involvement of female youth on different programs to maximize involvement and develop a sense of inclusivity. Future studies should explore additional factors influencing mobile phone dependence, such as personality traits, social dynamics, and cultural influences.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study has been reviewed and evaluated by the University of the Assumption Research Ethics Board (UAREB) before the data gathering procedure. Documents are submitted and procedures are strictly followed by the researchers in full compliance with the UA REB requirements.

Informed Consent Process, Duration of Participation, and Withdrawal Criteria

Respondents received the informed consent form at the beginning of the survey, serving as the basis for their decision to participate. The form emphasized confidentiality and outlined the study's purpose, overview of respondents' tasks, their rights to access their

information, request clarification, and the duration of data collection. Upon obtaining consent, hard copies of identical questionnaires are distributed in person to the respondents, accompanied by detailed instructions for completion. The respondents' expected participation took 20 minutes to finish answering the questionnaires. Respondents are allowed to withdraw from participating in the study anytime in any event that they become unwilling to continue or choose to withdraw voluntarily at any point.

Risk and Inconveniences

The risks associated with this study are negligible. Particularly, participation may require a 20 minutes time commitment for completing the questionnaire, which could potentially bring inconvenience to the respondents. In this aspect, the researchers emphasized the importance of the study and the potential benefit it may bring to the respondents. Moreover, while researchers enforced measures to protect respondents' data, there may be a possibility of a data breach, with data management protocol in place as discussed below.

Benefits of the Study

There are no direct monetary benefits and/or tokens given to the respondents. However, participating in the study can offer respondents valuable insights into the influence of mobile phone dependence on academic performance and quality of life among them. The respondents may also benefit from recommendations and activities formulated by the researchers from the data gathered in the study, which aimed at optimizing mobile phone usage, promoting academic performance and enhancing quality of life, which could prove beneficial to them.

Privacy, Confidentiality, and Data Management

The researchers ensured strict confidentiality of all provided data, including identities and personal information in accordance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012. Appropriate procedures to prevent data breaches were implemented, including restricting access to collected data to only the researchers, their adviser, their statistician, and relevant people involved in the study. In case of a data breach, prompt notification was given to the respondents, and authorities including the UA REB and the College of Nursing within 72 hours to ensure immediate mitigation.

In the completion of data collection, all information is securely stored for a period of two years and disposed of in accordance with school standards and legal regulations. Hard copy documents, such as questionnaires and consent forms, will be safeguarded in a secured and locked cabinet, while soft copies of data will be protected with password encryption.

After the required length of storage, soft copies of data should be permanently deleted from files and recycle bin and a screenshot were to be taken as evidence. Similarly, hard copies were to be securely destroyed using a paper shredder, with photo documentation

obtained as evidence of destruction. Respondents received advanced notification prior to disposal procedures.

Respondents may request a copy of their responses by contacting the designated focal person after data collection is complete.

Conflict of Interest

The researchers declared no conflict of interest in the actual conduct of the study. Though legible, the researchers did not participate as respondents of the research study.

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